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IMPROVING SECURITY OF COMPRESSOR STATIONS ON PIPELINES USING A COMPREHENSIVE MULTIFACTOR EXPERIMENT

Introduction

The Ukrainian transcontinental gas transportation system, created to supply Siberian gas to consumers in Western Europe, is currently operating under partial load due to well-known geopolitical events. Therefore, it is impossible to adequately assess its operational characteristics, including reliability indicators. However, the elimination of such an expensive and energy-intensive facility is not feasible, as it may be realistically used for transporting energy carriers on a transcontinental scale in the future. Hence, an important task at this stage is to assess the reliability indicators of both individual components and the system as a whole.

The trend of technical condition parameters of gas-pumping aggregates at compressor stations is governed by complex dependencies. To simplify the deviations of their parameters from nominal values, they are usually expressed with sufficient accuracy using simple approximating functions. For the development of methods to forecast the condition of gas-pumping aggregate elements, it is important to establish the form of the approximating function. Its choice affects the error, labor intensity of forecasting, and, ultimately, the entire process of managing the reliability indicators of compressor station equipment.

The reliability of the gas supply system and its components depends on various factors, including the level of operation and management of the system, the reliability of the equipment elements, and the structure and volume of the reserves. Key determining factors in the achieved level of operation, automation of system management, and equipment reliability are the reserves' volume and their structure, as well as the system's architecture. These factors can change either due to more rational use and distribution of costs for creating and

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developing the system, or through an increase in these costs. Thus, the reliability problem is a techno-economic issue (Sukharev, 1981).

Today's sustainable development of society is a priority development of mankind. It is based on balancing the mankind modern needs and protecting the interests of future generations. To balance the relationship between nature and humanity, it is necessary to ensure systematic coordination between the social, environmental and economic components, which is the main challenge in the management process (Horal, 2024).

One of the main indicators of the aggregate, determining its safe operation, is the reliability of the gas-pumping aggregate. The effectiveness of using the gas-pumping aggregate in the gas transportation system directly depends on its reliability. The reliability of a gas-pumping aggregate, like any technical object, is defined as its ability to perform specified functions, maintaining corresponding operational indicators over time. Depending on its purpose and operating conditions, reliability, as a comprehensive property, may include maintainability, durability, preservation, and failure-free operation, either separately or in specific combinations of these properties.

Scientific research on reliability has evolved in two main directions. The first is associated with the improvement of mathematical methods for reliability assessment, particularly for complex systems, with statistical processing of operational data and the development of complex system structures to ensure high reliability. The second direction is a result of studying the physics of failures (wear, corrosion, fatigue strength), developing calculation methods for heat resistance, wear, strength, etc., using technological methods that ensure the necessary reliability of machinery. Currently, there is a process of integrating these two directions, transferring rational ideas from one area to another, and forming a unified science of product reliability (Sukharev, 2000).

By using mathematical statistics and probability theory, as well as related disciplines, special calculation methods have been created and developed, addressing key aspects of the reliability problem of products. As academician B.V. Gnedenko rightly states, "mathematics is merely a tool for research and calculation, not an end in itself. The underlying section should always be the engineering problem, and the scientific apparatus that most closely matches the nature of the phenomenon being studied should be employed" (Kovalco, 2002). However, to form the theoretical foundation of this science, the development of mathematical methods in reliability theory is necessary, though not sufficient. Therefore, stochastic methods for studying the reliability of complex engineering systems with generalization of the results play an important role at this stage.

Main research objectives used on the aforementioned, the primary tasks of the study include analyzing the operational characteristics of gas compressor units to identify the reasons for deviations of actual repair cycles from the normative ones, using statistical analysis to assess the reliability parameters of gas compressor units at compressor stations, and mathematically modeling the impact of maintenance parameters on key economic indicators of the enterprise.

Research based on the consideration of design, construction, and operational factors that influence parameter changes, one can examine its deviation at any point in the service life as the sum of two quantities:

$$s(t) = c + Z \quad (1)$$

where: $s(t)$ – actual deviation of the parameter (significant positive continuous random variable), c - theoretical deviation of the parameter under the influence of internal, factory factors (significant positive continuous random variable), Z – deviation of the parameter under the influence of external, operational factors (continuous random variable).

The random variables c and Z can take various values, unknown until measurement. The value c forms the distribution of the parameter at fixed service intervals based on averaged results of element operation, which characterizes the average operational load; the value Z - the distribution of deviation of the actual parameter change from the averaged curve.

Equation (1) can be written at time t as the sum of two random variables:

$$s(t) = W_c f(t) + W_t^* f_1(t) \quad (2)$$

where: $f(t) + W_t^*$ and $f_1(t)$ – deterministic (non-random) functions that characterize the dependence of s and Z on service life t ;

W_c – random variable representing the rate of change of the parameter under the influence of internal factors, W_t^* – random variable for the deviation of Z with respect to the unit change in the parameter under the influence of external factors.

The first term $W_c f(t)$ is an elementary random function. All possible realizations of this function can be obtained from the function graph with a simple scaling of the ordinate axis. An elementary random function is the simplest among random functions. Here, W_c is a conventional random variable and $f(t) + W_t^*$ is a conventional non-random function.

A linear random function has the form:

$$s(t) = W_c(t) + Z(t) \quad (3)$$

Functions (2) and (3) can also characterize the change in the parameter of a specific element, i.e., a single realization. In this case, W_c is constant, while $Z(t)$ is a random

variable at time t . In the case of smooth or relatively smooth increasing realizations of parameter deviations of the element, and under approximating the real process of parameter change, the term $Z(t)$ can be considered zero. Thus:

$$s(t) = W_c(t) \quad (4)$$

In equation (3), $Z(t) = W_t^* f_1(t)$ is the function of the deviation of actual parameter values from the averaged smooth theoretical curve. Here, W_t can be regarded as a Gaussian-centered stationary or non-stationary process over time. It is Gaussian because, at any given moment, the function value is a random variable that follows a normal distribution.

When approximating the function of parameter change, the wear of machine parts is considered, during which a short-term sharp increase in the parameter is observed. However, the greatest interest lies not in the wear section but in the segment where the parameter approaches its critical value, as this is where failures occur (Kovalco, 2002). Therefore, the highest degree of approximation is desired in the range from the end of wear to the moment when the parameter reaches its critical deviation $-s_c$. In most cases, to achieve a sufficient match of theoretical and experimental curves in the mentioned range, the wear section can be neglected. Thus, the character of the function change in the wear section can be assumed to be similar to that in other sections:

$$s(t) = W_c(t) + Z(t) + \Delta\varphi \quad (5)$$

where: $\Delta\varphi$ is the quantity characterizing the wear of the element, numerically equal to the ordinate value at $t = 0$. It ensures a normal approximation of the parameter deviation from the end of the wear period to the moment the critical deviation s_c is reached.

The achievement of a critical value by the parameter results in the element's failure. The density distribution of wear until failure is determined based on the transformation theorem of random variables. For example, in the base function $s(t) = W_c(t)$, the term W_c is a random variable with a distribution density $\psi_0(W_c)$. The resource of an element with a rate of deviation W_c is expressed as a direct function:

$$t = s_c / W_c \quad (6)$$

Then, the density distribution of the resource for a fixed critical deviation s_c is determined as a function of the random argument:

$$\psi(t) = \psi_0[R(t)]R'(t) \quad (7)$$

where: $R(t)$ – the inverse function of $W_c = s_c/t$; $R'(t)$ – the derivative of this function with respect to t .

For a normal distribution:

$$\psi(t) = \frac{s_c}{\sigma_w t^{\alpha+1} \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp \left[-\frac{(s_c/t - m_w)^2}{2\sigma_w^2} \right] \quad (8)$$

where: m_w , σ_w are the mean and standard deviation.

For a Weibull distribution:

$$\psi(t) = \frac{K_b K_b s_c}{m_w t^{\alpha+1}} \left(\frac{s_c}{t}\right)^{b-1} \exp\left[-\frac{K_b s_c}{m_w t^\alpha}\right] \quad (9)$$

where: K_b is the gamma function with parameter b :

$$K_b = \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{b} + 1\right) \quad (10)$$

The resource distribution function in this case can be obtained by integrating equation (9) from 0 to t and will have the form:

$$F(t) = \exp\left[-\frac{K_b s_c}{m_w t^\alpha}\right]$$

After straightforward transformations for the average resource, we obtain:

$$T_{cp} = \left(\frac{K_b s_c}{m_w t^\alpha}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \Gamma\left(1 - \frac{1}{\alpha}\right) \quad (11)$$

In the simplest case, taking into account equation (2), the term $Z(t)$ can be written as:

$$Z(t) = W_t^* (W_c t^\alpha) \quad (12)$$

When forecasting the average statistical change of the parameter in the ensemble of identical elements, W_c and W_t^* are random independent variables at time t . When forecasting the realization of the parameter change in a specific element, they represent a constant value for this element, and W_t^* is random. Unlike W_c , which is constant for a specific element, W_t^* can take various values, changing over time. Therefore, for $W_t^* = 0$, the realizations of the parameter change appear as irregular broken curves.

Taking into account equation (12), the function (5) takes the form:

$$s(t) = W_c t^\alpha + W_t^* (W_c t^\alpha) = W_t^* (1 + W_c t^\alpha) \quad (13)$$

For an exponential function of parameter change:

$$s_1(t) = \alpha \exp(W_c t) - \Delta\varphi \quad (14)$$

After logarithm transformation, equation (14) becomes:

$$\ln[s_1(t) + \Delta\varphi] = \ln \alpha + W_c t \quad (15)$$

In this transformed form, W_c will characterize the random rate of parameter change, and $\ln \alpha$ is the rate of change of the parameter during the service life. The resource density distribution of the element, in the case of normal distribution of W_c , is given by:

$$\psi(t) = \frac{\ln(s_c/\alpha)}{\sigma_w t^2 \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left[-\frac{\left(\frac{\ln(s_c/\alpha)}{t} - m_w\right)^2}{2\sigma_w^2}\right] \quad (16)$$

By analogy, other approximating deviations of the parameter function can be determined, and resource estimates for the element can be derived. However, the use of different approximating functions, alongside the indicated advantages (improved approximation and forecasting accuracy), has a significant drawback. Each function requires its own calculation methods, forecasting tools, and appropriate formulas, tables, and nomograms, significantly complicating the forecasting process.

Therefore, after selecting and calculating the coefficients of any approximating expression, it should be transformed into a defined function for which a forecasting apparatus is developed. This is the only way to use a broad class of approximating expressions with relatively simple mathematical support for forecasting.

The proposed forecasting method for the gas compressor units resource was tested under the conditions of the Bohorodchany No. 21 compressor station of the “Soyuz” pipeline, which is equipped with 7 gas compressor units of the GCU-10 type.

For each installed gas compressor units, the efficiency coefficient was determined as the ratio of the useful power of the gas turbine unit to the input specific energy. The useful power of the gas turbine unit was defined as the power consumed by the centrifugal compressor, while the input specific energy was determined by the consumption and energy intensity of the fuel gas. The results are presented in graphical form in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Dependency of the efficiency coefficient of gas compressor units on service life

Rysunek 1. Zależność współczynnika sprawności agregatów sprężarek gazowych od czasu eksploatacji

As expected, the dependencies of the efficiency coefficient on the service life of the gas compressor units exhibit a decreasing trend. For the application of the proposed forecasting method for the unit's resource, the functional curve should show an increasing trend. Therefore, it was suggested to investigate the dynamics of energy losses in relation to service life, which is related to the efficiency coefficient through the following dependency:

$$\varepsilon = 1 - \eta \quad (17)$$

Based on the changes in efficiency coefficient as a function of service life, similar curves were constructed for energy loss changes. From their statistical analysis, the average energy consumption curve as a function of service life was derived. Using statistical data, which were processed by the least squares method, an approximating curve was obtained (Figure 2).

The time-dependent change in the average curve of the determined parameter will take the form of the following function:

$$S = s(\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \dots \alpha_n, t) \quad (18)$$

where: $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \dots \alpha_n$ – coefficients that take different values for each specific unit;

t – service life

Figure 2. Average statistical dependency of energy losses on service life

Rysunek 2. Średnia statystyczna zależność strat energii od czasu eksploatacji

The critical service life value is proposed to be determined as follows. For each unit, the critical value of each parameter is either set by the manufacturer (company) or based on operational experience. This means that each parameter has its own permissible value, which defines the safe operation of the unit. From the given value for each unit, the critical service life value is determined T_{KP} , the time after which elements that have failed should be replaced. For different m units, we will have a sequence: $T_{KP1}, T_{KP2}, \dots T_{KPM}$

It is clear that the service life corresponding to the average critical value for the average curve falls within the range $T_{KP1} \leq T_{KPMcp} \leq T_{KPM}$.

For a specific concept of the critical value of the determined parameter, we will replace s_{KP_GPU} with s_{KP_cp} and T_{KP} with T_{KPCp} their respective values. Let us assume that the function $s(\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \dots \alpha_n, t)$ determines the value T_{KP} . Then, we have:

$$s(\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \dots \alpha_n, t) = s_{KPCp}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \dots \alpha_n, T_{KPCp}) \quad (19)$$

In this case, the question arises regarding the accuracy of determining T_{KP} . Operational experience shows that there is a certain deviation between the calculated value T_{KP} and its statistical estimates, which is referred to as the calculation error. This can be determined as follows: Let for m units out of a total of M , on the basis of which the research was conducted, the expected remaining resource value τ was forecasted Δt , $T_{KP} - \tau = \Delta t$. For m working units, we have $\Delta t_1, \Delta t_2, \dots, \Delta t_m$, $T_{KPM} - \tau = \Delta t_m$. Then the average calculation error for the critical service life value is:

$$\varepsilon(\tau, t) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m |\Delta t_i - \Delta t| \quad (20)$$

By using the average statistical dependency of energy losses on service life, the equation for its approximation by a power function was derived:

$$\varepsilon = 0,6274 + 0,0017195t^{1,386} \quad (21)$$

This allowed, under the assumption of a Weibull distribution hypothesis, to calculate the average remaining resource for the compressor station units, which amounted to 27.8 thousand hours.

Discussion of Research Results: The majority of equipment at compressor stations is characterized by both physical and moral obsolescence. In this regard, one of the most significant tasks is the renewal of the gas compressor units fleet and upgrading their technical level to meet modern requirements. However, updating the gas-pumping aggregate fleet proves to be a labor-intensive task, as new equipment for compressor stations must fully comply with the technical and economic parameters of the gas transportation system. The implementation of such a project requires significant financial investments. Therefore, it seems more justified to use methods of restoring fixed assets, such as performing repair and maintenance work according to the manufacturer's recommendations, as well as conducting forced (emergency) repairs; carrying out modernization that involves the introduction of new technologies with partial replacement of parts and equipment to increase reliability, reduce operational costs, and extend the interval between repairs; and implementing reconstruction measures, which imply a complete replacement of outdated equipment with the latest models.

Depending on the type of repair, its complexity, and duration, expenses for conducting repair work and involving subcontractors are planned. Technical maintenance of gas-pumping aggregate is carried out by the operational service of the enterprise or a subcontractor with the appropriate license. Medium and major repairs are performed by specialized repair organizations. At the same time, annual maintenance costs for gas transport facilities increase by at least 10%.

The frequency of technical maintenance and repairs is determined based on the working resource and operational indicators, such as the number of "hot" startups and emergency shutdowns, as well as the downtime between consecutive services or repairs. If early

replacement of certain components of the unit is necessary, the nearest type of service or repair should be carried out according to the unit's service life.

The key indicators determining the need to withdraw equipment for repair based on its technical condition are the frequency and intensity of failures. The complexity of technological schemes for gas-pumping aggregates and drive systems, in particular, may cause failures that lead to equipment shutdowns (Pronikov, 1981) and significantly impact the performance of compressor stations.

When analyzing statistical data and assessing the reliability of gas supply facilities, it is recommended to use composite reliability indicators. The main of these is the availability factor, which determines the probability that the throughput capacity will function properly. Another indicator may be the operational readiness factor, which determines the probability that the gas supply facility will be operational at any given time. This factor is calculated as the ratio of operating time to time spent in standby mode, divided by the total calendar time. Additionally, the technical utilization factor may be used, which is determined as the ratio of average operating time to the sum of average operating time and downtime. These indicators are important when evaluating reliability; however, in this context, they will not be discussed further.

A gas compressor unit, like any technical device, goes through three most characteristic periods from the beginning to the end of its operation, which are represented by the Weibull distribution. [Gnedenko, 2005].

$$f(t, \lambda, k) = \frac{k}{\lambda} \left(\frac{t}{\lambda}\right)^{k-1} e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\lambda}\right)^k}, \quad (22)$$

where: $k > 0$ determines the shape of the graph, and $\lambda > 0$ scale parameter.

The run-in period is characterized by a high failure rate caused by deviations from the requirements of design and technological documentation, which are distributed according to the Weibull distribution and are eliminated through the introduction of technological run-in (Step'yuk, 2009).

The normal operation period is characterized by minimal and constant failure rates. These failures are considered sudden, random in nature, and are generally distributed according to the exponential distribution; the failure rate remains approximately the same. The aging period is characterized by a sharp increase in the failure rate, which is distributed according to the normal distribution; the failure rate continuously increases.

Based on actual data on the operation of GTK-10I gas compressor units at the Bohorodchany compressor station of the "Soyuz" pipeline, as presented in , the dependence of the probability of failure on

operating time was constructed based on (22), which is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Dependence of the probability of failure on operating time

The presented methodology compares the residual resources of GTK-10I gas compressor units at compressor station No. 21 of the “Soyuz” pipeline. The results are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Distribution of residual resources among units.

It should be noted that the proposed methodology for calculating the composite reliability indicator (the availability factor), which is based on accounting for the total forced downtime, including downtime due to the lack of spare parts, does not align with the logical definition of this indicator. The duration of such downtimes can amount to several hundred hours. In the case of averaging these indicators, their inclusion may distort the actual picture, as this time should be excluded from the statistics. It is recommended to account for this time separately when calculating reliability indicators, particularly in cases of fewer backup gas-pumping aggregates.

The aging process that occurs during the operation of traditional compressor station equipment can be conveniently expressed through the failure rate function. In simpler cases, when aging processes are

absent, a constant failure rate can be used, corresponding to an exponential distribution. The parametric families of failure-free operation time distributions, where the failure rate changes monotonically over time (increases or decreases), include the Weibull distribution, gamma distribution, and truncated normal distribution. In reliability theory, the Weibull-Gnedenko [Gnedenko, 2005]

Results of the statistical data verification regarding the recovery time of gas pumping units after failure indicate that the failure-free operation time follows an exponential distribution law. If downtime due to the absence of spare parts for the recovery of gas pumping units is included in the analysis, a log-normal distribution law might be applicable. However, it is crucial to note that this downtime is random, and it should not be included in the recovery flows nor considered in the context of distribution laws.

Conclusion

The proposed methodology, based on a probabilistic approach to the aging processes of elements in the gas transportation system during operation, allows for forecasting the trends in the reliability indicators of gas compressor units, which ultimately determines the ability to ensure gas supply to consumers.

To maintain the reliability indicators of elements in the gas transportation system, particularly gas compressor units, it is recommended to optimize their maintenance procedures. Significant improvement in the quality of repair work at this stage, under current conditions, is technically infeasible and economically unjustifiable.

Abstract: This paper addresses the evaluation of the key reliability indicators for gas-pumping aggregates at compressor stations in the natural gas transmission system, based

on mathematical modeling of aging processes and the recovery of equipment characteristics. The main factors influencing the system's operation and the reliability of equipment at the current level of system management are the volume of reserves and their structure. These factors may change either due to more rational use and distribution of costs for the creation and development of the system or through an increase in these costs. Therefore, the issue of reliability is, in essence, a techno-economic problem. Thus, the research problem includes analyzing the operational characteristics of gas-pumping aggregates to identify the causes of deviations in actual repair cycles from standard ones, applying a stochastic approach to evaluating the reliability parameters of gas-pumping aggregates at compressor stations, and mathematically modeling the influence of repair service parameters on the main economic indicators of the gas transmission system. To achieve this goal, it is proposed to determine the approximating deviations of parameter functions and derive assessments of the element's resource. However, the application of approximating functions has significant drawbacks, as forecasting machine states and using corresponding formulas complicates the forecasting process. Therefore, after selecting and calculating the coefficients of any approximating expression, it should be transformed into a defined function, for which a forecasting mechanism is developed. This is the only way to use a broad class of approximating expressions with relatively lightweight mathematical support for forecasting. The proposed method of forecasting gas-pumping aggregate resource was tested under the conditions of the compressor stations of the "Soyuz" and "Urengoy-Pomary-Uzhgorod" pipelines in the context of a comprehensive multifactor experiment conducted at gas transportation system facilities in Ukraine. This allowed for the prediction of reliability trends of gas-pumping aggregates at compressor stations, which ultimately determines the potential to meet consumers' gas demands. To maintain the reliability indicators of the elements in the gas transportation system, it is recommended to optimize their maintenance procedures, as significantly improving the quality of repair work at this stage, under current conditions, is technically unfeasible and economically unjustifiable.

Keywords: Gas-pumping aggregate, reliability indicators, mathematical modeling, probabilistic approach, maintenance optimization.

Streszczenie: Niniejszy artykuł dotyczy oceny kluczowych wskaźników niezawodności agregatów sprężających w stacjach kompresorowych systemu przesyłu gazu ziemnego, opierając się na matematycznym modelowaniu procesów starzenia i odzyskiwania charakterystyk urządzeń. Główne czynniki wpływające na funkcjonowanie systemu oraz niezawodność urządzeń na obecnym poziomie zarządzania to wielkość rezerw oraz ich struktura. Czynniki te mogą ulegać zmianie w wyniku bardziej racjonalnego wykorzystania i dystrybucji kosztów na tworzenie i rozwój systemu lub poprzez zwiększenie tych kosztów. W związku z tym problem niezawodności ma w istocie charakter techniczno-ekonomiczny. Przedmiotem badań jest analiza charakterystyk eksploatacyjnych agregatów sprężających w celu zidentyfikowania przyczyn odchylenia rzeczywistych cykli napraw od standardowych, zastosowanie stochastycznego podejścia do oceny parametrów niezawodności agregat sprężający gaz w stacjach kompresorowych oraz matematyczne modelowanie wpływu parametrów serwisowania na główne wskaźniki ekonomiczne systemu przesyłowego gazu. W celu realizacji tego celu zaproponowano określenie aproksymacji odchylenia funkcji parametrów i wyprowadzenie ocen zasobu elementów. Zastosowanie funkcji aproksymacyjnych ma jednak istotne wady, ponieważ prognozowanie stanów maszyn i stosowanie odpowiednich wzorów komplikuje proces prognozowania. Dlatego po wybraniu i obliczeniu współczynników dowolnego wyrażenia aproksymacyjnego należy je przekształcić w zdefiniowaną funkcję, dla której opracowuje się mechanizm prognozowania.

Tylko w ten sposób można wykorzystać szeroką klasę wyrażeń aproksymacyjnych przy relatywnie uproszczonym wsparciu matematycznym dla prognozowania. Proponowana metoda prognozowania zasobu agregat sprężający gaz została przetestowana w warunkach stacji kompresorowych gazociągów "Sojuz" i "Urengoy-Pomary-Uzhgorod" w ramach kompleksowego wieloczynnikowego eksperymentu przeprowadzonego na obiektach systemu przesyłowego gazu w Ukrainie. Pozwoliło to na przewidzenie trendów niezawodności agregatów sprężających w stacjach kompresorowych, co ostatecznie określa potencjał zaspokojenia zapotrzebowania na gaz ze strony konsumentów. W celu utrzymania wskaźników niezawodności elementów systemu przesyłowego gazu zaleca się optymalizację procedur ich konserwacji, gdyż znaczne poprawienie jakości prac naprawczych na tym etapie, w obecnych warunkach, jest technicznie niemożliwe i ekonomicznie nieuzasadnione.

Słowa kluczowe: agregat sprężający, wskaźniki niezawodności, modelowanie matematyczne, podejście probabilistyczne, optymalizacja konserwacji.

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